

Association Rule Mining and Statistical Validation for Prognosis of Infectious Diseases in Kathmandu, Nepal

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Abstract

Infectious diseases present a significant public health challenge, especially in urban areas like Kathmandu, Nepal, where rapid urbanization and high population density are responsible to spread the infectious diseases. This study uses Association Rule Mining (ARM) on inpatient records from Sukraraj Tropical and Infectious Disease Hospital, Teku, focusing on dengue, kala-azar, and scrub typhus. The research explores association rules related with patient outcomes to identify key prognostic patterns. Results show that patients with moderate hospital stays and no comorbidities, particularly males with dengue and females with scrub typhus, consistently had high discharge rates, which highlight the strong role of demographic and clinical factors in achieving positive treatment results.

To ensure accuracy, the association rules created by the Apriori algorithm were checked for statistical significance using the Chi-square test, then validated with bootstrapping to confirm stability across resampled datasets. The findings aim to support public health efforts, resource allocation, and disease control strategies. By leveraging ARM, this research offers an in-depth understanding of disease patterns associated with infectious disease prognosis in Kathmandu hospitals, contributing to better healthcare decision-making.

Keywords: *association rule, data mining, infectious disease, prognosis*